

Appendix 4. School authorities interview guide

This guide is divided in three main parts: first impressions, Achieving lesson objectives, Intended and unintended effects, adaptations to the lesson delivery and factors affecting delivery and scale up of the intervention.

Instructions for interviewer (moderator)

- Review the lesson plan before the interview
- Share the interview objectives. (Remind them that we are exploring the how he has achieved teaching the lessons, effect of the intervention to students and external factors that might have affected the teaching the lesson)

Instructions for Note taker

- Make the recorder ready for discussions
- The teacher may be referring on any lesson in an interview. Note takers should be diligent about noting which lesson the teacher is referring to.

User test materials:

- Interview Guide
- Notebooks
- Pens/pencils
- Identification card (mandatory- if visiting study participant for the first time)
- Covid-19 PPE (masks, sanitizer etc)
- Voice recorder/camera

Interview session details

Date:	
School:	
School type:	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Private <input type="checkbox"/> Government-aided 1. <input type="checkbox"/> Low performing <input type="checkbox"/> High performing
Facilitator/moderator	
Observer/note taker(s)	

Head teacher/Director of studies details (Refer to the teacher details for received)

participant study ID	
Role of the participant at school	
Type of technology teacher used	<input type="checkbox"/> laptop <input type="checkbox"/> smart phone <input type="checkbox"/> pad <input type="checkbox"/> projector

Introduction to the school authority (head master/director of studies)

We would like to extend our sincere appreciation for having completed teaching the “Be smart about your health” lessons during this term.

The purpose of this discussion is to explore with you as a leader at your school some of the factors that might have affected teaching and learning from the lessons.

We would like to know about things that might have contributed to good (effective) teaching, and positive learning experiences for the students, but also about things that you felt were problematic.

There is no right or wrong answer.

The information you give us will help us to understand the advantages and disadvantages of the “Be smart about your health” lessons and how they could be integrated in the curriculum and be scaled up country wide and elsewhere.

Please remember that whatever information we get from you will be kept confidential.

Section A. SCHOOL SYSTEM AND ENVIRONMENT

Question	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>1. What were your first thoughts about the “Be smart about your health” lessons teaching them in your school?</p>		<p>Begin with an open question (also listen especially for new themes that aren’t covered below)</p>
<p>2. Based on both your current position as the school head, and your school’s recent participation in teaching the lessons, what were your main challenges when introducing lessons into your school timetable?</p> <p>Prompts:</p> <p>Is the timetable flexible enough to accommodate the introduction of new material, such as these lessons?</p> <p>Was the ICT equipment (computer and projector) always available when needed?</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School organization and management - Competing priorities
<p>3. What policies or regulations if any by the Ministry of Education or REB do you think may have affected the way the “be smart about your health” lessons were delivered at your school?</p> <p>Prompt:</p> <p>Remember the lessons were to be delivered in English, twice a week, for five weeks, using a projector.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policies/Regulations
<p>4. Taking into consideration your experience as the school head, what should be in place to enable more schools like yours to introduce the “Be smart about your health” lessons into their timetable?</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scaling up

Section B. FEEDBACK ON CHOICE MATERIALS AND THE TEACHER

<p>5. Based on the information you have about the “Be smart about your health” resources and your interaction with the resources:</p> <p>Do you think the material is appropriate for Senior two students in your school?</p>		<p>- Appropriateness of thematerial</p>
<p>6. In your opinion, to what extent are the “Be smart about your health” lessons compatible with the current school curriculum?</p> <p>Prompt:</p> <p>What would need to change for the lessons to fit into the current curriculum?</p>		<p>Compatibility with the curriculum</p>
<p>7. In your opinion, do you think you teacher was motivated to teach the lessons?</p> <p>Why? Or why not</p>		<p>motivation</p>
<p>8. Do you think the teacher was able to deliver the lessons as planned?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What helped you deliver the lessons as planned? ▪ What made it difficult to deliver the lessons as planned? ▪ Were there specific parts of the lessons that you could not implement in the classroom, or that were difficult to implement? Then probe as to why ▪ What might help teachers deliver these lessons well? 		

Section C. Intended effects, unintended effect and transfer

Question(s)	Observer notes	Adverse effect and transfer
<p>9. Have you experienced or observed the lessons having <u>any advantages</u> to students? If so, please tell us about it.</p> <p>Probe</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assertiveness (students asking more questions and not taking things for granted) ● Improved decision---making (students making more thoughtful and informed decisions) <p>Creativity (Thinking outside the box)</p>		intended effects
<p>10. Have you experienced or observed the lessons having <u>any disadvantages</u> to students? If so, please tell us about it.</p> <p>Prompt:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Misunderstanding ● Conflict (students and teachers, parents, or other authorities) ● Distraction ● Stress, or other uncomfortable thoughts or feeling ● Wasted time or resources 		unintended effects

<p>11. Have your students <u>used anything they learned</u> in the lessons at home with family/ when they are with friends? If so, please tell us about it.</p> <p>Prompt:</p> <p>-Have they <u>taken something learned</u> in the lessons <u>and used it in a different subject or field</u>?</p>		Transfer of learning
<p>12. Do you have any suggestions of other possible good or bad impacts that “Be smart about your health” resources or learning these concepts might have on people?</p>		Intended and unintended effects

Section D. Immediate discussion after the session

<p>Observer notes</p>